

DUAL IN PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS DOLZARB PROBLEMS OF ORGANIZING EDUCATION

Hamzayev M.

Head of the Department of Labor Market Analysis and Cooperation with
Employers of the Department of Higher Education, Science and
Innovation of Samarkand Region

Soliev A.T.

deputy director for production education,

Meliboev A.A.

deputy director for work with youth,
Samarkand Transport Technical University

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Abstract. In this article, the adoption of the Decision No. 163 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2021 "On the measures for the organization of dual education in the system of professional education", analyzes and suggestions about the current problems of the organization of dual education in professional educational institutions based on the decision are presented.

Keywords. Education, dual, specialist, enterprise, student, science, activity, theoretical, practical, training, contract, need.

In our country, more attention is being paid to the development of the education sector and the formation of a well-rounded generation than ever before. At this point, it is necessary to recognize that the law "On Education" recently adopted in literally renewed Uzbekistan was a foundation for real reforms in the field of education, an important practical work.

Article 17 of the law discusses dual education, "Dual education is aimed at acquiring the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities by students, the theoretical part of which is carried out on the basis of the educational organization, and the practical part is carried out at the place of work of the student."

The procedure for organizing dual education is determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The adoption of the Resolution No. 163 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2021 "On measures for the organization of dual education in the professional education system" indicates that practical work on the organization of dual education has begun in our Republic.

Dual education is the basis for the training of specialists within the framework of mutual education, involving the educational infrastructure of students and the employer in the educational process. Professional Understanding bilateral education as an experience of relations, transfer of production skills for work, interaction on the subject linked with the general principles of relations . In the process of dual education, the student simultaneously applies the theoretical knowledge acquired in the enterprise or organization and strengthens the skills and qualifications of the specialty. In this, students develop the ability to disseminate theoretical knowledge and concepts aimed at understanding a real, specific production process. The principle of determining practical activity in the scientific process is based on the main goal of knowledge. The dual educational process justifies the objectivity of knowledge

with practical activity, which is the power of learning, and is a means of verifying its reality. This is reflected in the dialectical relationship between theory and practice.

Dual training is tailored to the needs of a particular company

The innovative form of organizing professional training, which includes the mutual influence of educational and production spheres, is understood in the preparation of specialists of the first degree. In this case, the common goal of the educational institution and production enterprises is the integration of the process of training authorized specialists of certain skills with social compositional characteristics. The basis of this integration reflects the community of goals, content of values, and activities carried out in the conditions of bilateral training. With this cooperation of the educational institution and the enterprise, the social order for the high-quality and quantitative higher education system is determined. According to the scientists who studied the system of personal and craft education based on the stylistic principle of opportunity, the main forms of two-way education are: It is an institution of social partnership. It is given to the employer with a clear distinction of interests and obligations of each partner. Two-way training ensures that certain enterprises interested not only in the results of the training of specialists, but also in the training process and the content of its organization, are involved in the training process. This is determined by the importance of dual education, which makes it possible to fill the gap in the training of a specialist and the fields of education. Taking into account the theoretical and stylistic, psychological and philosophical foundations, the professional training of specialists in the conditions of two-way teaching is considered. It is appropriate to focus on four main components:

1. Motivational (achieving success; learning to read motivation; level of professional satisfaction, rationalization of scientific activity interest through offers).
2. Organizational and management component (visible leadership ability to be communicative qualities; organizational characteristics).
3. Cognitive (assimilation of knowledge in professional activity; education give independence in receiving).
4. Scientific component (level of participation in scientific purposes; enterprise direction of practical innovation projects for solving problems).

Analysis of the problem of training mature specialists is extensive as a process, it allows to study the needs of the state and society.

The main tasks of this analysis mean the following:

- training of production specialists and problem solving to determine the possibilities of using the obtained results;
- bilateral internal and analysis of international experience;
- effective for training specialists for the bilateral field justification of the need to create technologies.

Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2021 "Measures for organizing dual education in the professional education system about" based on the Resolution No. 163 "Dual in the professional education system" Regulation on the procedure for organizing education" was developed and this According to the regulations, from the 2021/2022 academic year, dual in the professional education system education is organized. Dual education is education tailored to your field it is a system that leads along with working in the organization. Dual education by the administrations and interested ministries to

establish the medium the need for joint personnel is determined and an offer is prepared. High and the Ministry of Secondary Special Education by July 1 of each year for dual education personnel determines the educational institutions to be prepared. Selected education Institutions accept students according to established quotas. Education institutions enter into contracts with organizations that need personnel.

The contract is concluded between the organization and the student. This is for the student a certain workplace is allocated in the organization. Students at least two a week One day he studies, the other days he works. Payment to the student for the days of work is paid Thus, by defining the main concepts of dual education teaching in the context of bilateral training for specialists We tried to open the content. Dual education perspective Ensuring the professional training of specialists is a complex process. systematic theoretical studies in order to increase its efficiency analysis is appropriate.

Used literature:

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